

Understanding the influence of Ti content on mechanically alloyed and sintered CoCrFeNiTi_x high entropy alloy

Petr Kratochvíl^{a,*}, Hana Thürlová^a, Vojtěch Nováček^a, Angelina Strakošová^a, Jaroslav Čech^b, Miroslav Karlík^b, Petr Hausild^b, Jiří Čapek^b, Filip Průša^a

^a University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Department of Metals and Corrosion Engineering, Technická 5, Prague 6, 166 28, Czechia

^b Czech Technical University in Prague, Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Trojanova 13, Prague 2, 120 00, Czechia

ABSTRACT

The influence of a wide range of Ti content on the microstructure and properties of CoCrFeNiTi_x alloy prepared by mechanical alloying and spark plasma sintering was investigated. The content of Ti ranged from $x = 0.44$ – 2.15 . A gradual change in the phase composition from sole FCC solid solution to fully intermetallic alloy, comprising (Co, Ti)-rich Laves and (Fe, Cr)-rich σ phases, was observed during the increasing Ti content. The Ti showed major FCC solid solution strengthening at 10 at.% and secondary phase strengthening after the partial formation of intermetallic phases at the content of 15 at.%, reaching compressive yield strength of 2157 ± 70 MPa and hardness of 968 ± 10 HV1. Higher amounts of Ti led to further strengthening, increasing the hardness at the expense of ductility. The wear resistance followed the hardness and increased with Ti content, reaching $2.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{N}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ for the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}. The Ti content also affected the mechanism of wear shifting from mainly adhesive to abrasive wear, showing the presence of oxide debris and cracks, directly pointing to oxidation wear and thermal fatigue.

1. Introduction

High entropy alloys (HEAs), or multi-principal element alloys (MPEAs), are progressively growing in the focus of metallic materials research. Due to their compositional variability, new possible applications are discovered over time, attracting scientists' attention from different branches of material science. All this is further enhanced by manufacturing technology innovation, enabling the processing of materials hardly treatable by conventional methods.

A major part of the HEAs are alloys based on CoCrFeNi because this system can dissolve substantial amounts of other elements, forming FCC or BCC solid solutions or their mixtures accordingly. This unexpected behaviour sparked interest when first discovered with the well-known HEA CoCrFeNiMn [1]. Among other elements, aluminium [2], titanium [3], niobium [4] or molybdenum [5] are also somewhat soluble. Due to the high plastic strain of the CoCrFeNi, the addition of other elements started to be approached as an opportunity for precipitation hardening either in as-prepared or thermally treated samples. Adding both Al and Ti is particularly interesting [6–10]. Various formations of hard intermetallic phases such as L1₂, B2 or Laves phases [11–13] enhance the mechanical properties, achieving great tensile and compressive mechanical characteristics. An increase of 100% in the ultimate tensile strength was recorded in some cases [12], while others achieved compressive strengths around 3000 MPa [14,15].

Although the incorporation of Al alone in the CoCrFeNiAl alloy was thoroughly studied, information is rather scarce for its CoCrFeNiTi counterpart. Generally, cast CoCrFeNiTi_x is composed of FCC solid solution supplemented with σ and Laves phases [16,17], which amount depends on the overall content of Ti. Despite these findings, pure FCC CoCrFeNiTi alloy was also reported [8]. The precipitation of the intermetallic phases directly affects the mechanical properties, increasing the hardness, yield strength and ultimate strength at the expense of plasticity [16,17]. The microstructure of the cast alloy endures high-temperature annealing almost unchanged [18], whereas rapidly solidified alloys undergo precipitation at high temperatures [19]. The mechanically alloyed CoCrFeNiTi_x phase composition was reported to be solely FCC solid solution or a combination of FCC and BCC solid solutions. It is quite usual that there are differences in the phase composition after mechanical alloying (MA) however, even the phase composition of the heat-treated alloys, i.e. sintered or annealed, differs significantly. The only common sign is the FCC phase, which can either stand alone or is supplemented with the BCC phase or σ -phase [20–23].

The addition of Ti within the CoCrFeNi alloy may become beneficial in multiple ways, including lowering the wear rate [23–26], increasing hardness [24,25,27], and enhancing the erosion and corrosion resistance [25,27,28] while being thermally stable up to 700 °C [26]. All these properties make the CoCrFeNiTi_x alloy promising for coating applications.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: kratochs@vscht.cz (P. Kratochvíl).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2025.03.032>

Received 3 December 2024; Received in revised form 9 February 2025; Accepted 4 March 2025

Available online 6 March 2025

2238-7854/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Table 1

Alloys composition overview.

Molar ratios	Ti content (at.%)	Ti content (wt.%)
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.44}	10	8.6
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.71}	15	13.0
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.00}	20	17.5
CoCrFeNiTi _{2.15}	35	31.4

The papers published on CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys prepared by MA are very scarce, mainly covering the preparation of the alloy for laser cladding, which significantly affects the prepared powders as they are melted during the process. Nevertheless, the MA significantly impacts the overall properties of the alloy and can promote solubility in the solid state. Therefore, this study focuses on preserving the effect of MA on the properties of CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys through the sintering consolidation. The main goal of this work was to explore the influence of Ti content on the microstructure and mechanical properties of MA and sintered CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys. For this purpose, four different CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys ($x = 0.44; 0.71; 1.00; 2.15$) were prepared with the Ti content ranging up to the top concentration of 35 at.%.

2. Experiment

The set of four different CoCrFeNiTi_x ($x = 0.44; 0.71; 1; 2.15$) alloys was prepared by MA of commercially available pure powders of each element. The content of each element was based on the amount of Ti in the alloy (see Table 1 for the atomic and weight percentages of Ti in the alloys). Amounts of other elements were balanced equally. A weight of 20g of the powder mixture was put into the milling vessel made of AISI 420 stainless steel, the same material as the milling bodies. As a process control agent, 0.8 g of N-heptane was added to the powder mixture to prevent agglomeration and cold-welding of the powder mixture to the walls and milling bodies. After sealing the vessel, it was flushed for 2 min with argon (99.996%) having a flow rate of 2 l min⁻¹ to displace the air from the vessel and further prevent oxidation during the alloying process. The MA was carried out with a balls-to-powder weight ratio of 15:1 at a speed of 400 rpm for 6 h straight. The mode of the milling was set to 30-min intervals with 10-min breaks and rotation reversal after each

milling interval.

The MA powders were compacted with spark plasma sintering (SPS, FCT Systeme HP D 10) using 10 g of the prepared powder inserted into a 20 mm diameter graphite die. The compaction temperature of 1000 °C was reached with a heating speed of 200 °C min⁻¹. After reaching the compaction temperature, a pressure of 48 MPa was applied, and the sample was sintered for 10 min. The sintering chamber was evacuated before compaction.

The chemical composition of the powder alloy was determined with scanning electron microscopy and electron dispersive spectrometry (SEM + EDS, JEOL JSM-IT500HR with JEOL JED-2300 EDS) analysis. Phases present within the prepared materials were identified through X-ray diffraction (XRD, PANanalytical X'Pert PRO, Co K α , $\lambda = 1.7903 \text{ \AA}$) and their respective amounts were obtained with standard Rietveld method. Based on the experimental results of XRD analysis was estimated a theoretical phase composition for an alloy with maximum content of the σ -phase. A function of each phase wt.% on the Ti concentration was found. From the derivation of the function for the σ -phase, the maximum content of this phase with respective Ti content was found. The content of other phases was then calculated from the estimated Ti concentration.

The morphology of powders and microstructure was studied using SEM (as mentioned above) and for element distribution mapping was used Tescan Lyra, 20 kV with OXFORD Instruments INCA 350, 80 mm² EDS. The powder particle size was measured using image analysis, where diameter of 60 particles was measured in total. For the microstructure observation, the samples were first ground on SiC papers (400–2500 grit) and then polished with 2 μm polycrystalline diamond paste, followed by final polishing on Eposal Al₂O₃ suspense with 0.06 μm grain size (QATM). The microstructure was also examined using scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM, JEM-2200FS, JEOL, Tokyo, Japan, 200 kV) equipped with an energy dispersion spectrometer (EDS, Centurio, JEOL, Tokyo, Japan). A Ga + focused ion beam (FIB, Quanta DualBeam, FEI, Hillsboro, OR, USA) was used to prepare the STEM lamella.

To determine the elastic moduli, nanoindentation (Anton Paar, NHT², Berkovich indenter) was used applying a 10 mN load with 10s loading/unloading and 5s of hold. Nine measurements were used to

Fig. 1. XRD diffractograms of the CoCrFeNiTi_x MA powders and compacted alloys.

Table 2

Summary of the phase composition of CoCrFeNiTi_x compact samples (in wt.%) (based on standard Rietveld method).

	FCC	Laves-C14	σ-FeCr	TiC	Ti ₃ O
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.44}	94.5	–	–	5.5	–
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.71}	58.3	22.2	14.1	5.3	0.1
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.00}	39.6	31.5	21.9	6.9	0.1
CoCrFeNiTi _{2.15}	–	79.3	17.3	2.2	1.1
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.40} (theoretical)	16.0	52.4	25.7	balanced	

calculate the mean value. Nanoindentation was also used to measure the microhardness of the MA powders and compact samples. The measurement was performed under the same conditions, with the only difference being 20 measurements for the MA powders to obtain an average value. A hardness tester with a Vickers indenter (Anton Paar, MHT) was used to evaluate the hardness of compact samples, with 1 kg of load and 9 measurements in total. The compressive tests were performed on the LabTest 5.250SP1-VM machine with a deformation speed of 10^{-3} s^{-1} . The specimens for compressive tests were block-shaped with a height of 1.5 factor the dimension of the base side length. At least three specimens were measured for each alloy to obtain sufficient statistics. Tribology tests (TRIBOTester, Tribotechnic) were carried out to determine the wear rate of the specimens. The tests were done against an Al₂O₃ ball with a load of 5 N moving in a linear mode, having a track length of 5 mm. The sliding speed was set to $15 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and the total distance of the test was 20 010 mm, providing enough time to obtain an equilibria state of the wear. The section area of the worn track was measured on three different areas with profilometer, and obtained values were used for calculation of the wear rates, which average values are then mentioned within the present manuscript.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Chemical and phase composition

The XRD diffractograms of the prepared MA powder CoCrFeNiTi_x ($x = 0.44; 0.71; 1.00; 2.15$, further denoted by their Ti molar ratio) alloys and their sintered equivalents (MA + SPS) are shown in Fig. 1, while the phases content results of compacted samples are summarized in Table 2. At first sight, there is a visible trend in the phase composition evolution with the increasing Ti content. The CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} is composed solely of FCC solid solution (ICDD card no. 00-047-1405, space group Fm-3m) originating from the CoCrFeNi alloy [4,29]. Despite the phase transformations after Ti addition in other HEAs [30,31], no change in the phase composition was detected in our case, and therefore, the Ti remains soluted in the FCC solid solution. However, increasing the content by another 5 at.% of Ti promotes the change of the phase composition and results in the formation of hexagonal Laves phase, with a structure of Co₂Ti (ICDD card no. 00-005-0719, space group P6₃/mmc) and tetragonal σ-phase mainly enriched in Fe and Cr (ICDD card no.

00-005-0708, space group P4₂/mnm). Increasing the amount of Ti, the intensity of the FCC phase progressively diminishes until the complete disappearance in the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}.

Contrary to that, the amount of the Laves phase increases with increasing Ti content and becomes the majority phase in the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} with 79.3 wt%. Considering the amount of σ-phase, there is not a clear trend as with the already mentioned phases, the content increases up to CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00}, where it reaches 21 wt% and then is reduced to 17 wt% in the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}. Both the σ-phase and the Laves phase increase their content at the expense of the FCC solid solution. While the FCC and Laves phase's content shows maxima at the opposite ends of the Ti concentration, for the σ-phase, it can be assumed there is an obvious maximum in the interval of 20–35 at.% of Ti. The maximum value was estimated based on the experimental results of XRD analysis and supplemented by the content of other phases to get an overall theoretical composition. The maximum was theoretically estimated to be 25.7 wt% of the σ-phase, with the Ti content reaching 25.9 at.%. The corresponding weight percentage of the FCC and Laves phase is 16 and 52.4 wt%, respectively, for this content of Ti. The whole sum is balanced with the content of carbides and oxides as they are also present in the alloy (Table 2). It can be assumed that the reason for the decrease is the preferential formation of the Laves phase, which, after reaching the status of the major phase, further suppresses the formation of the σ-phase.

Compared to the available data on MA + SPS CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys, although they are very scarce, there is quite good agreement with the work of Zhang et al. [32], who prepared an alloy through vacuum hot-press sintering. A similar phase composition was also reported by Zhiqiang et al. [23], with the Co_{0.5}CrFeNiTi_{0.5} alloy being composed of the FCC solid solution and the σ-phase, despite that they prepared an alloy with a slightly different composition. A mutual consensus among the phase composition can be found when cast alloys are taken into account [5], with the only difference of secondary phases emerging at lower Ti content in cast alloy than in MA + SPS alloy [17] as the maximum Ti solubility in cast alloy is around 3 at.% [3]. Considering the phase composition of the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} alloy, it might look similar to the CoCrFeNi alloy, as both are formed of the FCC solid solutions, usually coupled with a lesser amount of carbide particles in case of MA and sintering [33,34]. Nevertheless, it is evident that the FCC phases must have different lattice parameters due to the dissolution of Ti in the case of CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} alloy, which increases the lattice strain and inevitably affects the mechanical properties of the alloy.

Besides the mentioned phases, all the MA + SPS alloys contain a certain number of carbides, which are formed during the sintering process because the powder is enclosed in graphite foil to prevent interaction with an SPS mould and pushers. On top of that, the amount of carbides depends on the thickness of the layer being ground off the material after sintering, as more carbides are formed on the surface of the sample. The origin of the Ti₃O detected in the alloys comes from the “preoxidized” powders, which tend to form more oxides due to their

Fig. 2. Morphology of MA powders with mean particle size (μm , upper right corner): a) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}; b) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71}; c) CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00}; d) CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}.

Table 3

The chemical composition of compacted samples obtained with SEM + EDS (in at.%).

	Co	Cr	Fe	Ni	Ti	O	Si
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.44}	20.0 ± 0.2	21.4 ± 0.1	24.7 ± 0.2	19.8 ± 0.2	9.8 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.1
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.71}	19.0 ± 0.2	19.9 ± 0.1	22.2 ± 0.1	19.0 ± 0.2	15.0 ± 0.1	3.6 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 0.1
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.00}	18.4 ± 0.2	19.3 ± 0.2	20.8 ± 0.2	18.1 ± 0.2	18.2 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.2	2.0 ± 0.1
CoCrFeNiTi _{2.15}	14.9 ± 0.1	15.6 ± 0.1	16.3 ± 0.1	14.9 ± 0.1	32.9 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1

high specific surface area, let alone Ti and Cr, with high oxygen affinity.

As shown in Fig. 1, the patterns of MA powders correspond to the patterns of sintered samples. The reflections of the powder samples embrace the bulk reflections as the powder peaks are broadened and slightly shifted. This refers to the MA powders' high lattice strain and smaller crystallite size. Moreover, the peak shift towards lower angles is

associated with lattice expansion due to the increased solubility of Ti within the FCC phase. Titanium has the largest atomic radius among the elements present, contributing significantly to the expansion of the lattice. It is clear that the Ti_{0.44} powder contains FCC phase, whose intensity decreases at the expense of other phases emerging with the increase of Ti content. Distinguishing these phases would be of high uncertainty due to the comprisal of several phases (which are visible in the bulk samples diffractograms); thus, we preferred not to specify them.

The trend in the phase evolution is also clearly visible from the morphology of MA powders shown in Fig. 2. Due to the highest content of plastic FCC solid solution in CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}, the particles are the biggest, and their edges are more rounded. One can see the progression of the size and surface morphology through Fig. 2a to c, in which the size of the particles is remarkably smaller with more faceted surfaces from the frequent fragmentation caused by the significant increase in fragile intermetallic phases, starting the transition from ductile into a brittle behaviour. The mean particle size of CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} ($233 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$) was reduced to $19 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ for CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}, with the most significant size reduction observed for the transition between CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71} and CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} before reaching sort of steady state. Despite the disappearance of the FCC phase in the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}, the difference in the powder morphology from CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} is not that noticeable,

Fig. 3. The SEM micrographs of the MA + SPS alloys with respective details in the top right corner: a) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}; b) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71}; c) CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00}; d) CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}.

Fig. 4. The SEM + EDS element distribution maps on the particle boundaries of the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}.

apart from the higher number of the smallest fraction of particles, which signifies that the CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} alloy is already saturated with the intermetallic phases.

The chemical composition of the MA + SPS alloys was analysed with EDS area analysis, and the results are shown in Table 3. The values approximately follow the desired composition, although some impurities are involved, as is usual for MA [35,36]. The content of Fe is slightly higher due to the contamination of the alloy with the material of the jar and milling balls. On the other hand, the content of Ti is quite precise; only at higher values, it was slightly below the theoretical values, which is probably due to the formerly mentioned pre-oxidation of powder particles, which is also most likely the case for lower values of the Co and Ni elements. Besides that, a minor amount of Si was found in the alloy, which comes from the cleaning process of the milling equipment. Despite careful precautions taken to minimize its content, completely avoiding Si contamination is nearly impossible.

3.2. Microstructure

The SEM micrographs of the MA + SPS alloys with respective details are shown in Fig. 3. In the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} micrograph (Fig. 3a), a very fine-grained microstructure is visible with slightly pronounced bands, documenting the formation of microstructure during MA, typical for ductile materials. The contrast was formed due to the different etching speeds of areas with different crystallographic orientations or differences in the deformation energy imposed during MA. A boundary of the powder particle is noticeable; however, the particles are several times bigger than in the other prepared alloys; thus, it is not as evident as in the other micrographs, where the particle boundaries are clearly visible. The boundaries are rich in Ti, as is visible from the SEM + EDS analysis (Fig. 4). Despite the higher concentration of oxygen or carbon is not evident, referring to the TEM + EDS results (Fig. 6), it can be assumed that the particles on the boundaries are mainly titanium carbides and oxides, as they are frequently present in the microstructure. The TEM results also suggest that unreacted Ti particles can be present in these areas. As was already mentioned, the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} alloy is single-phased, which is clearly visible from the overview, where no particles with different BSE intensity signals, i.e. different chemical compositions, are visible like in the other three alloys, although the detailed window shows some differences, which might be caused by different etching speed. It has a homogeneous, ultrafine microstructure with hardly distinguishable grains. Contrary to that, distinct particles with different chemical compositions are visible in Fig. 3b and c, corresponding to the increase of the number of phases with the Ti content. The powder particles become smaller as the alloy becomes more brittle due to the formation of intermetallic phases. This makes the borders between the particles more noticeable in the micrographs of CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} and CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} (Fig. 3c and d). The microstructure of CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} (Fig. 3d) is composed of 2 phases, the main being the Laves phase with islands of the σ -phase. Generally, the microstructure of all the samples is homogenous with ultrafine-grain character, which can be attributed to the fast SPS consolidation that successfully minimizes the

microstructural coarsening. Black spots appearing across the microstructures along with the nanometric particles revealed by the magnified parts are most likely carbide and oxide particles as the SEM + EDS element distribution maps (Fig. 5) signify. Otherwise, some of these spots might be connected to internal microporosity, which was pronounced by the chemical interaction with the polishing suspension.

The SEM + EDS element distribution maps are presented in Fig. 5. The CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} alloy is homogeneous, with a uniform distribution of all the elements. However, spots with a slightly higher intensity of Ti are noticeable in the micrograph. It seems like it could be the signal coming from the TiC particles, as it is the only secondary phase comprised in the sample, based on the XRD data shown before (Fig. 1). The maps of the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71} and CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} (Fig. 5b and c) are more explicit as these alloys are formed of more phases. There is a connection between Fe and Cr concentrations, following each other trend of increase/decrease according to the presence of the σ -phase. Opposing these elements is the concentration of Ti, which is enriched exactly in the spots where Fe and Cr are depleted. The higher concentration of Ti corresponds to the Laves phase as the intensity further increases in the CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} (Fig. 5c), although the Co is not well pronounced. Looking at the concentration of Ni, it may substitute the Co in the Laves phase as the Ni–Ti pair mixing enthalpy is highly negative [3], and no NiTi-rich R-phase was found in our samples, apart from the cast alloys, where it occurs quite frequently [16,18]. Otherwise, the areas with higher Ni content are connected to the FCC phase, showing a decrease of other elements in the solid solution due to the formation of intermetallic phases. This suggestion is supported by the element map of the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} (Fig. 5d), where no areas with higher Ni content are visible due to the absence of the FCC solid solution. The brighter particles in the microstructure of CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} are σ -phases being enriched in Cr and Fe, whereas the main Laves phase is rich in Ti, Ni and Co. However, the elements can be mutually substituted in either phase because of their similar characteristics [16]. This would also correspond to a rather poor Co and Fe element distribution maps resolution in Fig. 5d.

Several STEM + EDS elemental maps were recorded on the CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} FIB lamella. One is presented in Fig. 6. The numerous dark particles contain mainly titanium, carbon, and oxygen. The quantification of their composition, including adjacent matrix phases is given in Table 4, presenting the average values obtained from 15 measurements (pop-up areas marked in red in Fig. 6). The average Ti/C ratio (at. %) is 1.3, suggesting that the dark particles are mainly TiC. The oxygen content in the particles is about 7.7 at. %, so there are also oxides of excess titanium. Several analysed particles had a Ti/C ratio equal to 2, indicating that the particles also contained unreacted Ti. In the particle areas, matrix alloy elements were also detected in higher amounts for small particles spanning less important parts of the lamella thickness. The matrix mainly contains the Laves phase (Ti and Si-rich), σ -phase (Cr and Fe rich), and Ni-rich FCC phase (in lesser volume in the micrograph area). These findings suggest that the pre-oxidized powder is the root cause of the high concentration of homogeneously distributed carbide-oxide particles in the microstructure of prepared alloys. Former oxide particles were principally reduced to carbides due to the direct contact

Fig. 5. The SEM + EDS element distribution maps of the alloys:
 a) $\text{CoCrFeNiTi}_{0.44}$; b) $\text{CoCrFeNiTi}_{0.71}$; c) $\text{CoCrFeNiTi}_{1.00}$; d) $\text{CoCrFeNiTi}_{2.15}$.

Fig. 5. (continued).

Fig. 6. STEM high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) micrographs and corresponding energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) maps of the CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} high-entropy alloy. Red lines in the micrograph indicate the boundaries of pop-up areas used to quantify the chemical composition from EDS map data cubes; the results are summarized in Table 4.

with graphite during sintering, causing a carbon diffusion to the alloys.

3.3. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties obtained with nanoindentation are

summarized in Table 5. The first two columns compare the hardness of the MA powder with the MA + SPS alloys. Unsurprisingly, the hardness increases with the Ti content, which is in accordance with other results, reporting the Ti being responsible for increasing the overall content of intermetallic phases, thus increasing the hardness and brittleness of such

Table 4

The chemical composition from STEM + EDS maps of the CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} alloy in at. % (average values from 15 read-outs from several maps, not only from Fig. 6).

	Co	Cr	Fe	Ni	Ti	O	C	Si
Particles	4.2 ± 2.2	4.0 ± 3.1	4.7 ± 3.1	3.5 ± 2.2	42.5 ± 5.6	7.7 ± 2.8	32.8 ± 7.4	0.6 ± 0.8
Laves phase	21.8 ± 1.3	10.0 ± 1.6	15.2 ± 1.3	17.7 ± 1.3	19.8 ± 1.0	1.7 ± 1.1	7.7 ± 3.9	6.1 ± 0.6
σ-phase	19.7 ± 1.1	21.1 ± 1.1	25.8 ± 2.1	19.6 ± 1.4	4.4 ± 1.2	0 ± 3.3	8.4 ± 3.3	1.0 ± 0.5

Table 5

Hardness comparison of the MA powders and compacted samples and Elastic moduli of the compacted samples (all measured with a load of 10 mN).

	Powders	Compacts		Ref.
	Hardness (MPa)		Elastic modulus (GPa)	
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.44}	9383 ± 476	8070 ± 212	247 ± 12	This work
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.71}	9676 ± 2361	9963 ± 843	257 ± 6	This work
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.00}	10802 ± 976	12625 ± 257	269 ± 17	This work
CoCrFeNiTi _{2.15}	12050 ± 1418	15428 ± 733	266 ± 9	This work
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.3}		3589 ^a	–	[16]
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.5}		5060 ^a	–	[16]
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.5}		2942 ^a	–	[38]
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.0}		4962 ^a	–	[38]
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.7}		6110	148	[17]
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.0}		8410	215	[17]
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.2}		9320	232	[17]
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.0}		12935	182	[43]

^a The approximate values extracted from available diagrams.

alloys [16,17,37,38]. but more interesting is the change in the trend when we compare hardness before and after sintering. For the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}, the hardness decreases after SPS, which is caused by the grain growth and partial relaxation of the lattice strain of the FCC solid solution during the SPS. The values before and after sintering are almost the same for the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71} due to the precipitation of the intermetallic phases, which compensate for the softening processes occurring during the SPS. With further increase of Ti, the intermetallic phases become dominant, changing the difference between the powder and the compacts in favour of the latter mentioned. The values of nano hardness are accompanied by broad error ranges, especially in the case of powder particles, as their analysis is linked with certain difficulties, which can affect the measurement. Embedment of the powder particles in resin brings uncertainty of entirely wetting the particles and of the remaining depth of the particle as indentation edges can deviate the values. Another aspect is the microporosity of the particles or the dislocation density, which affects the obtained values [39]. One can see that the error range of compacted samples decreases at least by 50%. Nevertheless, the nanoindentation is sensitive to the microstructure, phase composition and even crystal orientation [40,41] of the analysed materials; therefore, higher deviation of the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71} might be caused by a more even ratio of FCC and intermetallic phases. On the other hand, the wider span of CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} alloy, in which the FCC phase is no longer present, might be caused due to the overall brittleness of the alloy because around some of the indents was registered crack formation. The cracks were probably formed due to further increment of the hardness of the Ti_{2.15} alloy, while the elastic modulus is nearly the same as in the previous alloys as it was found a relation between the crack formation and elastic modulus/hardness ratio [42]. All the

Table 6

Comparison of the mechanical properties of CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys (CYS – compressive yield strength, UCS – ultimate compressive strength, HV1 – Vickers hardness using 1 kg load, ± stands for confidence interval with α=0.05).

	CYS (MPa)	UCS (MPa)	Plastic deformation (%)	HV1
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.44}	1430 ± 57	1676 ± 165	7.1 ± 3.9	703 ± 24
CoCrFeNiTi _{0.71}	2157 ± 70	2443 ± 116	1.3 ± 0.3	968 ± 10
CoCrFeNiTi _{1.00}	–	1977 ± 448	–	1136 ± 8
CoCrFeNiTi _{2.15}	–	1188 ± 265	–	1340 ± 31

Fig. 7. The compressive stress-strain diagram of MA + SPS CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys.

prepared alloys have a high elastic modulus (shown in the last column) rising with the content of Ti. The Elastic modulus is higher compared to other CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys prepared by other methods [17,43]. The elastic moduli follow the increase in hardness, which corresponds to the findings of Regent and Musil [44,45]; nevertheless, a bigger difference between the Ti_{1.00} and Ti_{2.15} alloys was anticipated as the phase composition changed entirely.

The general mechanical properties of the prepared alloys are summarized in Table 6. As outlined in the previous table, the hardness of the alloys increases with Ti content and corresponds to the amount of hard intermetallic phases within the microstructure. The CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}, based on its phase composition, took over the hardness of the Laves phases, reaching 1340 ± 31 HV1 [46–48]. Even though it is almost twice as high as the hardness of the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} (703 ± 24 HV1), the hardness of the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} is even more impressive considering it is an FCC solid solution alloy as the high hardness of HEAs is usually connected to the BCC solid solution, leaving FCC HEAs far behind [49, 50]. The solid solution strengthening is clearly visible when the hardness of the Ti_{0.44} alloy is compared to the hardness of CoCrFeNi, which reaches values of around 370 HV [33,34]. This alloy also has a higher hardness compared to cast specimens with similar Ti content, which reached around 600 HV [16,18]. The addition of Ti resulted in a major hardness increase of 265 HV in the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71} alloy, attributed to the formation of nearly 40 wt% of hard intermetallic phases. However, it is impressive that the alloy preserved some residual plasticity at this hardness, retaining more than 50 wt% (see Table 2) of plastic FCC solid solution.

The compressive stress-strain diagram of the MA + SPS compacts being tested at laboratory temperature is shown in Fig. 7. It

Fig. 8. a) Coefficient of friction diagram; b) Comparison of wear rate; of CoCrFeNiTi alloys.

demonstrates good compliance with the phase composition. During the elastic deformation phase, the alloys are well distinguished by their elastic moduli, which corresponds to the nanoindentation results of elastic moduli stated in the previous paragraph (Table 5). The CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} achieved CYS and UCS of 1430 ± 57 MPa and 1676 ± 165 MPa, respectively, and was the only alloy showing proper plastic deformation during the test. Despite this alloy being FCC, it shows a high level of solid solution strengthening. The main contributions to the strengthening are the lattice strain and grain size refinement imposed during the MA [51] and the Ti substitutional strengthening, further promoting the lattice strain [17,52]. The MA + SPS alloy exhibits more than 500 MPa higher CYS and approximately 170 MPa higher UCS compared to the cast CoCrFeNiTi_{0.5} counterpart [16]. On the other hand, it showed approximately 6 % lower fracture strain. A major increase in CYS and UCS by more than 700 MPa was observed as the Ti content in the MA + SPS alloy raised to 15 at.%, reaching 2157 ± 70 MPa and 2443 ± 116 MPa, respectively. This increase is attributed to the formation of hard intermetallic Laves and σ -phases, which, due to different crystallographic lattice structures compared to the FCC solid solution, impede the dislocation movement on the interfaces of the particles. The strengthening also heavily impacts the ductility, reducing it down to only 1.3 %.

In comparison with a four-element CoCrFeNi alloy, which exhibits a yield strength of 978 MPa [34], a substantial increase was recorded in the case of the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}, reaching nearly 500 MPa more. A cast CoCrFeNiTi_{0.7} alloy with the same phase composition achieved the CYS and the UCS of only 919 and 1872 MPa [17], respectively. However, the high strength values of the MA + SPS sample are at the expense of ductility. Equivalent mechanical properties were achieved by a cast CoCrFeNiTi_{1.2}, which contains approximately 8 at.% more Ti [17]. The strengthening of the MA + SPS samples cannot be entirely attributed to the already mentioned substitutional strengthening and grain refinement. The combination of MA + SPS also leads to the formation of fine carbides in the microstructure, providing another strengthening contribution. Further increasing the Ti content results in the complete loss of plasticity, but the remains of the FCC phase in CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00} provided more cohesion, which led to higher UCS compared to the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}. Considering the phase composition, one can see that the higher the content of the Laves phase, the lower the average value of the alloy's UCS. Apart from that, the Ti_{1.00} alloy showed not only higher UCS but also higher values of the confidence interval, which might be attributed to competing crack propagation origins resulting in their swift progression.

The next two diagrams (Fig. 8) summarize the studied tribological properties of the CoCrFeNiTi samples. The friction coefficient curves (COF), including average COF values and corresponding wear rate values, are shown in Fig. 8a and b, respectively. Two stages of the COF curves can be distinguished. The initial stage, characterized by the sharp increase of COF caused by the disruption of the original surface,

increases the frictional resistance until a dynamic equilibrium between the surface and the indenter ball is reached, marking the steady wear stage, where the COF stabilizes and undergoes more gradual changes. It can be seen that the hardness of the Ti_{2.15} alloy affected the initial stage, during which it took slightly more time to break the surface of the alloy and reach a steady state. In the steady state, all the curves follow an oscillating pattern due to the accumulation and removal of the wear debris. As most of the parameters affecting the COF [53], including surface roughness, are negligible due to the same measurement conditions, it depends mainly on the wear mechanisms. During the steady state, a combination of different wear mechanisms, among which an adhesive, abrasive, oxidative and three-body, are applied, each with a different rate based on the phase composition and mechanical properties of the alloy, as will be discussed further. The Ti_{0.44} is more prone to adhesive wear due to the highest content of the plastic FCC phase. A bigger contact area of the counter-body increased the adhesion, which, together with plastic deformation of the surface and oxidation of the accumulated debris, resulted in the highest COF of 0.645. The Ti_{0.44} exhibited the highest porosity (reaching 5%) than the rest of the alloys, which probably affected the resulting value of COF and the wear itself. In theory, the continuousness of the debris layer might be interrupted due to entrapment of the debris in the cavities, deteriorating the formation of the protective oxide layer, which forms in the following alloys. Higher porosity can also decrease the heat dissipation in the material, increasing the surface temperature of the wear track and possibly softening the plastic FCC phase, followed by an adhesion increase. That would explain the highest phase COF of all the alloys, as there is not a clear trend with increasing Ti content. Both the Ti_{0.71} and Ti_{1.00} alloys had similar COF courses with intensive up and down fluctuations during the steady state. These are probably connected to the repetitive formation and destruction of an oxide film on the surface. The formation of an adhered oxide film in the wear track has a protective character for a certain period, during which significantly decreases the COF. Nevertheless, the protective layer is not stable because of the stress build-up due to the imposed fatigue and thermal strain, followed by crack formation and subsequent destruction of the layer. Exposure of the alloy surface increases the COF, further amplified by the oxide layer debris abrasion, inducing higher friction forces between the alloy and the counterpart body [54]. The Ti_{0.71} alloy achieved the lowest COF of 0.573, which might be attributed to the combination of higher hardness but still quite high content of the FCC phase, suppressing a major involvement of only one of the mechanisms. Because of the high content of intermetallic phases and high hardness of Ti_{1.00} and Ti_{2.15}, it is expected that the abrasive wear played a major role in the wear of these alloys. From the wear rate diagram (Fig. 8b) is visible that from the Ti_{0.71}, the COF inversely rises to the wear rate values. As expected, following Archard's law [55], the wear rate decreases with increasing sample hardness, reaching its minimum of $2.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{N}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ for

Fig. 9. The SEM micrographs of the wear track morphology and details in top left corner: a) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}; b) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71}; c) CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00}; d) CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}.

the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} alloy. The wear rate evolution forms a parabolic trend, with the biggest absolute decrease occurring between the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} and CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71} alloys. Simultaneously, the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} alloy exhibited the largest relative reduction of wear rate from the preceding alloy, with a decrease of nearly 73%. Both alloys with higher Ti content achieved more or less similar results compared to other CoCrFeNiTi_x alloys prepared by a combination of MA and laser cladding [26,56]. Comparing the prepared alloys with CoCrFeNi counterpart, the alloy without Ti had a wear rate of $81.4 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{N}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ [57], but it should be noted that the tests were carried out at different conditions of higher load and sliding speed. Nevertheless, notably different results were published in another study, where the CoCrFeNi alloy achieved a wear rate of $2.9 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{N}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ at 5 N load but with different sliding speeds and counterbody material [58]. Although this

value of wear rate almost approaches the value of the Ti_{2.15} alloy, the set of test parameters is quite different, making it hardly comparable.

The micrographs of the wear track morphology are shown in Fig. 9. An intensive material transport and plastic deformation can be observed in Fig. 9a. At the same time, the absence of multiple scratches with wide and shallow furrows indicates adhesion wear as the main mechanism for the CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}. During the wear of ductile sample, the loosened material adheres to the track surface, increasing the friction heating, which leads to an intensive oxidation of the debris as confirm the SEM + EDS maps of the Ti_{0.44} alloy (Fig. 10a, maps of the Ti_{0.44} and Ti_{2.15} two alloys were selected, because they represent the minimal and maximal Ti concentration and different wear mechanisms). Besides high concentration of oxides, the debris also comprised higher carbon concentration, which refers to present carbides, coming from the

Fig. 10. The SEM + EDS element distribution maps of the worn surface of the: a) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}; b) CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}.

microstructure as was found by the TEM observation (Fig. 6). The same oxidation phenomenon was already documented on HEAs tribologically tested under the same conditions accompanied with similar appearance of oxidized debris along the track [59]. Formed hard oxide particles further increase the wear rate due to the three-body abrasion mechanism as is documented in the detailed cut-out. The highlighted rectangle documents a specific surface morphology, which comes from the plastic deformation caused by fatigue. This kind of morphology is regarded as an indicator of great abrasive resistance [60]. From the tested samples, the Ti_{0.44} alloy had the largest amount of debris located along the track and heavily accumulated on both ends of the track. As the hardness increases with Ti content, scratches and deeper furrows appear (Fig. 9b), suggesting higher engagement of the three-body abrasion. Discontinuous layers of adhered material are visible in the track, signifying the dominance of the adhesion wear, as in the previous case. Another similarity is a considerable amount of oxidized debris in the track. A notable difference in the track morphology is visible for the Ti_{1.00} alloy (Fig. 9c), as no signs of plastic deformation are noticeable, suggesting a transition of the main wear mechanism to a strictly abrasive [24,56]. The track is quite rough with deep scratches, but the surface is uniform and the amount of debris is restricted to a couple of particles. As the true surface

of the alloy is exposed, original particle boundaries, which were observed in the micrograph (Fig. 3), appear in the track. The boundaries do not affect the wear itself but because they represent an inhomogeneity in the microstructure, they might concentrate the stresses and thus induce cracking in the later stages of the wear. This phenomenon increases its importance for the Ti_{2.15} alloy (Fig. 9d). The stress concentration, including thermal stresses introduced during the sliding, leads to crack formation due to thermal cycling. These cracks further propagate as a result of combined repeated thermal and mechanical loading, exacerbated by the inherently brittle behaviour of the Ti_{2.15} alloy. Severe cracking of the track surface is visible, which has already resulted in spallation of loosened pieces. Even though the CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} wear rate was the lowest, it is more than probable that with increased time or load, the alloy will eventually fail due to intensive spallation. The surface after wear was uniform, with a lot of scratches, which were not so distinctive because of their shallow character due to high hardness of the alloy. It is supposed that three-body wear participates to a larger extent, as the alloy is formed primarily of hard intermetallic phases, which undergoes the spallation and then are transported along the track. The abrasion was accompanied by oxidative wear as is visible from the oxygen contrast in Fig. 10b.

Fig. 11. The schematic evolution of the wear mechanism of the: a) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44}; b) CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71}; c) CoCrFeNiTi_{1.00}; d) CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}.

The schematic evolution of the wear mechanism capturing the progress of wear for each alloy is shown in Fig. 11. The wear behaviour was strictly dependent on the phase composition and related mechanical properties. Therefore, a clear transition of the wear behaviour was registered between the Ti_{0.44} and Ti_{2.15} alloys despite several wear mechanisms engaged. The main wear mechanism of the Ti_{0.44} was adhesion with microplastic deformation; nevertheless, the oxidation wear increased the wear rate due to three-body wear. Regardless of the debris oxidation, the presence of porosity negatively affected the formation of the protective oxide layer, resulting in the highest COF among tested alloys. The content of the FCC phase was shown to have a crucial role in the protective oxide layer formation, as both the Ti_{0.71} and Ti_{1.00} had similar COF curve trends. The adhesive wear remained dominant in the case of Ti_{0.71}; nevertheless, the amount of debris significantly decreased compared to the preceding alloy. An increase in the content of intermetallic phases turned the wear mechanism to be mainly abrasive for the Ti_{1.00} alloy as loosened hard intermetallic phases stimulated the three-body wear through direct scratch generation. The fatigue wear accompanied by delamination and abrasion were the main mechanisms of the Ti_{2.15}. The accumulated fatigue with thermal cycling resulted in severe cracking perpendicular to the wear direction, causing a loosening of the cracked areas and, finally, delamination. The Ti_{2.15} achieved the best wear resistance of the investigated alloys; however, the mechanism indicates that it would lead to fast destruction of the surface with prolonged wear time.

4. Conclusion

The influence of Ti on the microstructure and properties CoCrFeNi-Ti ($x = 0.44; 0.71; 1.00; 2.15$) prepared with MA + SPS was studied in this work. The key findings are stated below.

- The phase composition evolves with the increase of Ti content, starting with a strengthened FCC solid solution for CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} up to a fully intermetallic CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15} alloy, composed of (Co, Ti)-rich Laves and (Fe, Cr)-rich σ phase.
- The size and morphology of the MA powders vary depending on their phase composition; however, all of the alloys showed ultrafine-grained microstructure.

- The highest compressive strength was achieved in CoCrFeNiTi_{0.71}, with CYS and UCS of 2157 ± 70 MPa and 2443 ± 116 MPa; nevertheless, the ductility was reduced to a bare minimum.
- The wear rate decreases with Ti content, achieving a minimum value of $2.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{N}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ for CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}, as it was inversely related to the hardness (1340 ± 31 HV1).
- The wear mechanism changes according to the phase composition, shifting from primarily adhesive wear with minor abrasive wear in CoCrFeNiTi_{0.44} to a predominantly abrasive mechanism with severe cracking due to thermal cycling in CoCrFeNiTi_{2.15}.

Data availability

The data used in this article are available in the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14234564>.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (project no. 21-11313S) and by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

References

- [1] Yeh JW, et al. Nanostructured high-entropy alloys with multiple principal elements: novel alloy design concepts and outcomes. *Adv Eng Mater* 2004;6(5): 299–303.
- [2] Kao Y-F, et al. Microstructure and mechanical property of as-cast, -homogenized, and -deformed Al_xCoCrFeNi ($0 \leq x \leq 2$) high-entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2009; 488(1):57–64.
- [3] Karimzadeh M, et al. Effects of titanium addition on the microstructure and mechanical properties of quaternary CoCrFeNi high entropy alloy. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2022;856:143971.

- [4] Liu WH, et al. Effects of Nb additions on the microstructure and mechanical property of CoCrFeNi high-entropy alloys. *Intermetallics* 2015;60:1–8.
- [5] Shun T-T, Chang L-Y, Shiu M-H. Microstructure and mechanical properties of multiprincipal component CoCrFeNiMox alloys. *Mater Char* 2012;70:63–7.
- [6] Wang S, et al. Influence of Al content on high temperature oxidation behavior of AlxCoCrFeNiTi0.5 high entropy alloys. *Vacuum* 2019;163:263–8.
- [7] Jiang S, et al. Studies on the microstructure and properties of AlxCoCrFeNiTi1-x high entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2018;741:826–33.
- [8] Zhang KB, et al. Microstructure and mechanical properties of CoCrFeNiTiAlx high-entropy alloys. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2009;508(1):214–9.
- [9] Zhou Y-k, et al. Microstructure and sliding wear behavior of HVOF sprayed Al(1-x)CoCrFeNiTi high-entropy alloy coatings. *Mater Lett* 2022;314:131929.
- [10] He JY, et al. Precipitation behavior and its effects on tensile properties of FeCoNiCr high-entropy alloys. *Intermetallics* 2016;79:41–52.
- [11] Gu X, Zhuang Y, Jia P. Evolution of phase, microstructure and mechanical properties of as-cast Al0.3CoCrFeNiTi high entropy alloys. *Mater Today Commun* 2022;31:103328.
- [12] He JY, et al. A precipitation-hardened high-entropy alloy with outstanding tensile properties. *Acta Mater* 2016;102:187–96.
- [13] Lu Y, et al. Balanced mechanical properties of Al0.3CoCrFeNiTi high-entropy alloys by tailoring Ti content and heat treatment. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2023;866:144677.
- [14] Zhong X, et al. Microstructural features and excellent compression properties of a novel Al0.7CoCrFeNiTi0.3 high entropy alloy. *Mater Lett* 2021;286:129246.
- [15] Zhou YJ, et al. Solid solution alloys of AlCoCrFeNiTi with excellent room-temperature mechanical properties. *Appl Phys Lett* 2007;90(18):181904.
- [16] Shun T-T, Chang L-Y, Shiu M-H. Microstructures and mechanical properties of multiprincipal component CoCrFeNiTi alloys. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2012;556:170–4.
- [17] Chung D, et al. Influence of Ti addition on the strengthening and toughening effect in CoCrFeNiTi multi principal element alloys. *Metals* 2021;11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met11101511>.
- [18] Jiang L, et al. Annealing effects on the microstructure and properties of bulk high-entropy CoCrFeNiTi0.5 alloy casting ingot. *Intermetallics* 2014;44:37–43.
- [19] Zhang B, et al. Precipitation behaviors of the rapidly-solidified CoCrFeNiTi high-entropy alloy during aging treatment. *J Alloys Compd* 2024;970:172502.
- [20] Rogachev AS, et al. Long term stability of a high-entropy CoCrFeNiTi alloy fabricated by mechanical alloying. *J Alloys Compd* 2023;931:167470.
- [21] Haq MA, et al. Powder interface modification for synthesis of core-shell structured CoCrFeNiTi high entropy alloy composite. *Appl Surf Sci* 2020;506:144925.
- [22] Mishra RK, Shahi RR. Phase evolution and magnetic characteristics of TiFeNiCr and TiFeNiCrM (M=Mn, Co) high entropy alloys. *J Magn Magn Mater* 2017;442:218–23.
- [23] Fu Z, et al. Fabrication and properties of nanocrystalline Co0.5FeNiCrTi0.5 high entropy alloy by MA-SPS technique. *Mater Des* 2013;44:535–9.
- [24] Liu Y, et al. Microstructure, hardness, and tribological properties of CoCrFeNiX (X = Mo, Ti, W) high entropy alloy coating by red-blue composite laser cladding on copper alloy. *Surf Coating Technol* 2024;483:130761.
- [25] Gu Z, Xi S, Sun C. Microstructure and properties of laser cladding and CoCr2.5FeNi2Ti high-entropy alloy composite coatings. *J Alloys Compd* 2020;819:152986.
- [26] Li Y, et al. Microstructure, thermostability and tribological behavior of composite CoCrFeNiTi high-entropy alloy coatings fabricated by laser cladding. *Optik* 2023;283:170899.
- [27] Zhang S, et al. Investigation on solid particles erosion resistance of laser cladded CoCrFeNiTi high entropy alloy coating. *Intermetallics* 2021;131:107111.
- [28] Wang X, et al. Effect of Ti content on the microstructure and corrosion resistance of CoCrFeNiTi high entropy alloys prepared by laser cladding. *Materials* 2020;13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13102209>.
- [29] Vaidya M, Guruvadyathri K, Murty BS. Phase formation and thermal stability of CoCrFeNi and CoCrFeMnNi equiatomic high entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2019;774:856–64.
- [30] Fu Z, et al. Influence of Ti addition and sintering method on microstructure and mechanical behavior of a medium-entropy Al0.6CoNiFe alloy. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2014;619:137–45.
- [31] Chen Z, et al. Effects of Co and Ti on microstructure and mechanical behavior of Al0.75FeNiCrCo high entropy alloy prepared by mechanical alloying and spark plasma sintering. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2015;648:217–24.
- [32] Zhang X, et al. Mechanical properties of CoCrFeNi-X (X = Ti, Sn) high entropy alloy and tribological properties in simulated seawater environment. *Tribol Int* 2025;202:110306.
- [33] Olejarz A, et al. Cr-rich structure evolution and enhanced mechanical properties of CoCrFeNi high entropy alloys by mechanical alloying. *J Mater Res Technol* 2024;30:1490–504.
- [34] Li M, et al. Microstructures and mechanical properties of oxide dispersion strengthened CoCrFeNi high-entropy alloy produced by mechanical alloying and spark plasma sintering. *Intermetallics* 2020;123:106819.
- [35] Suryanarayana C. Mechanical alloying and milling. *Prog Mater Sci* 2001;46(1):1–184.
- [36] Moravcik I, et al. The origins of high-entropy alloy contamination induced by mechanical alloying and sintering. *Metals* 2020;10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met10091186>.
- [37] Wang K, et al. Microstructure and properties of CoCrFeNiTi high-entropy alloys fabricated by laser additive manufacturing. *Coatings* 2024;14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings14091171>.
- [38] Li H, et al. Effect of Ti on characterization and properties of CoCrFeNiTi high entropy alloy prepared via electro-deoxidation of the metal oxides and vacuum hot pressing sintering process. *Materials* 2023;16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16041547>.
- [39] Chikova OA, et al. Measuring the nanohardness of commercial submicrocrystalline aluminum alloys produced by dynamic pressing. *Phys Met Metallogr* 2014;115(5):523–8.
- [40] Rajesh Kannan A, et al. Microstructure and nanomechanical behaviour of wire-arc additive manufactured nickel-based superalloy C276. *Progress in Additive Manufacturing* 2024.
- [41] Zhang H, et al. Nanoindentation behaviors of the AlCoCrFeNi2.1 eutectic high-entropy alloy: the effects of crystal structures. *J Alloys Compd* 2024;1008:176535.
- [42] Song J-M, et al. Nanomechanical responses of intermetallic phase at the solder joint interface – crystal orientation and metallurgical effects. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2012;534:53–9.
- [43] Lian G, et al. Influences of Ti and Mo alloying on the microstructure and properties of laser cladding for CoCrFeNi high-entropy alloys. *J Mater Res Technol* 2023;27:5945–64.
- [44] Regent F, Musil J. Magnetron sputtered Cr Ni N and Ti Mo N films: comparison of mechanical properties. *Surf Coating Technol* 2001;142–144:146–51.
- [45] Musil J, et al. Relationships between hardness, Young's modulus and elastic recovery in hard nanocomposite coatings. *Surf Coating Technol* 2002;154(2):304–13.
- [46] Stein F, Leineweber A. Laves phases: a review of their functional and structural applications and an improved fundamental understanding of stability and properties. *J Mater Sci* 2021;56(9):5321–427.
- [47] Liu CT, et al. Physical metallurgy and mechanical properties of transition-metal Laves phase alloys. *Intermetallics* 2000;8(9):1119–29.
- [48] Qiao P, et al. Mechanical properties of σ -phase and its effect on the mechanical properties of austenitic stainless steel. *Coatings* 2022;12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings12121917>.
- [49] Tong C-J, et al. Mechanical performance of the AlxCoCrCuFeNi high-entropy alloy system with multiprincipal elements. *Metall Mater Trans* 2005;36(5):1263–71.
- [50] Guo S, Ng C, Liu CT. Anomalous solidification microstructures in Co-free AlxCrCuFeNi2 high-entropy alloys. *J Alloys Compd* 2013;557:77–81.
- [51] Zhang KB, et al. Nanocrystalline CoCrFeNiCuAl high-entropy solid solution synthesized by mechanical alloying. *J Alloys Compd* 2009;485(1):L31–4.
- [52] Wu B, et al. Influence of Ti addition on microstructure and mechanical behavior of a FCC-based Fe30Ni30Co30Mn10 alloy. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2016;676:492–500.
- [53] Blau PJ. The significance and use of the friction coefficient. *Tribol Int* 2001;34(9):585–91.
- [54] Li Y, et al. Mechanical properties and wear behaviors of FeCoNiCrMnTi high-entropy alloys manufactured by vacuum arc melting. *J Mater Res Technol* 2024;30:1962–77.
- [55] Archard JF. Contact and rubbing of flat surfaces. *J Appl Phys* 1953;24(8):981–8.
- [56] Liu H, et al. Microstructure and wide temperature range tribological properties of CoCrFeNiTi high-entropy alloy coating by laser cladding. *J Mater Eng Perform* 2024;34:1515–25.
- [57] Zhang Z, et al. Effect of C additions to the microstructure and wear behaviour of CoCrFeNi high-entropy alloy. *Wear* 2023;530–531:205032.
- [58] Zhang H, et al. Significant improvement in wear resistance of CoCrFeNi high-entropy alloy via boron doping. *Lubricants* 2023;11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/lubricants11090386>.
- [59] Průša F, et al. Microstructure and mechanical properties of in-situ SiO₂-reinforced mechanically alloyed CoCrFeNiMnX (X = 5, 20, 35 at.%) high-entropy alloys. *J Mater Res Technol* 2024;32:860–73.
- [60] Wang Z, et al. Achieving considerable wear resistance in new Ti-based high-entropy alloys through microstructural hardening by adding Nb. *Tribol Int* 2025;202:110379.